

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Interaction of Cobalt(II) with L-Tyrosine

H. C. MALHOTRA*, JAI PRAKASH and GIAN CHAND SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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The rate constants for the interaction of cobalt(II) with L-tyrosine have been obtained at $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO_3) using Aminco-Morrow stopped flow spectrophotometer. Study covered the pH range 6.10-6.90. Specific rate constants k_{12} , k_{43} and k_{34}/k_{23} for the cobalt-tyrosine interaction have been determined. Mechanism consistent with the kinetic data has been suggested.

THE complexing of metal ions by L-tyrosine has direct applications in many biological processes.

In order to understand the hydrolysis of proteins catalysed by carboxypeptidase A, it was established¹ that the action of carboxy peptidase A depends to a large extent on binding of metal ions to L-tyrosine. Similarly, the binding of metal ions to serum albumin, insulin and many protein complexes² shows that the metal ions are connected only with the tyrosine residue. A number of kinetic studies on the interaction of metal ions with amino acids and related compounds³⁻⁵ have shown that the rates of the interaction depend largely on the charge of the reacting ligand. According to Cassatt and Wilkins⁶, a ligand may exist in several tautomeric form, representing the reactivity of the ligand. The kinetic study of Ni^{II} with L-tyrosine has been studied by Malhotra and Jai Prakash⁶.

Review of literature reveals that no kinetic study on the interaction of Co^{II} with L-tyrosine has been conducted so far. Therefore, it was thought desirable to investigate the kinetics of interaction of Co^{II} with L-tyrosine, which has three functional groups, viz OH, COOH and NH_2 .

Experimental

L-Tyrosine (Koch-light), 2,6-lutidine (Merck-Schuchardt), KNO_3 (AnalaR) and bromothymol blue (Loba) were used.

Solution of Co^{II} ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) was prepared from $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck). Doubly-distilled water was used in the preparation of all solutions. The ionic strength of all reaction mixtures was kept constant at 0.1 M (KNO_3). Freshly prepared solution of L-tyrosine ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) was used in all the reactions.

An immersion type NBE (Germany) thermostat and a Radiometer pHM 26 pH meter were employed for rate studies. An Aminco-Morrow stopped flow spectrophotometer, was used for the purpose.

The transmittance changes were monitored at 620 nm when bromothymol blue (10^{-5} M) was added to L-tyrosine. Changes in transmittance for each run were traced out from the oscilloscope. The half-life times ($t_{1/2}$) were evaluated from the log ΔV versus time plots, ΔV 's being directly proportional to concentration changes. For every set, 10-15 runs were made and average half-life time calculated. These values were used to calculate the observed rate constants.

Results and Discussion

In order to understand the kinetics of interaction of metal ions by L-tyrosine, we utilised the values of microdissociation constants⁷ corresponding to each functional group of L-tyrosine. As can be seen that the phenolic group has least value of dissociation constant, and OH is weakly dissociated as compared to COOH and NH_2 groups. Therefore, it is expected that the phenolic group would not participate in complexation with the metal ions. The result is that only COOH and NH_2 groups in L-tyrosine play an important role in the complexation reaction. Kinetic study was made in the pH range 6.10-6.90.

Kinetics of Co^{II} -L-tyrosine interaction: The kinetics of the interaction of Co^{II} with L-tyrosine was investigated in the pH range as described above and at ionic strength 0.1 M. The temperature was maintained at $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$. Fig. 1 represents an oscilloscope trace of voltage versus time at pH 6.32. It is evident from Fig. 1 that there is only one reaction taking place. Cobalt(II)-L-tyrosine follows the overall differential rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Co}^{2+}]}{dt} = -\frac{d[\text{L-Tyrosine}]}{dt} \\ = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{L-Tyrosine}][\text{Co}^{2+}] = k'_{\text{obs}}[\text{L-Tyrosine}] \quad (1)$$

where, $k'_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Co}^{2+}]$.

It has been confirmed from the linear plot of log ΔV versus time. One such plot is shown in

Fig. 1. Oscilloscope trace of voltage vs time for the reaction of CoII with L-tyrosine at pH 6.82.

Fig 2. The second order rate constants k_{obs} for this reaction were calculated utilising the slopes of such plots. These values are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 2. The plot of $\log \Delta V$ vs time for CoII-L-tyrosine system at pH 6.82.

TABLE 1—OVERALL FIRST AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE INTERACTION OF CoII WITH L-TYROSINE AT DIFFERENT pH

$\mu = 0.1 M (KNO_3)$, $[L\text{-Tyrosine}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Temp. = $85 \pm 0.06^\circ$

Sl. no.	$[Co^{2+}] \times 10^3 M$	pH	$k_{obs} s^{-1}$	$k_{obs} \times 10^{-3} mol^{-1} s^{-1}$
1.	1.25	6.10	10.65	8.59
2.	1.25	6.25	12.67	10.16
3.	1.25	6.32	13.86	11.17
4.	1.25	6.48	14.48	11.63
5.	1.00	6.45	11.64	11.64
6.	1.00	6.48	13.30	13.30
7.	1.00	6.58	13.60	13.60
8.	1.20	6.63	16.75	13.96
9.	1.20	6.82	19.15	15.96
10.	9.00	6.84	15.99	15.99
11.	0.85	6.87	13.70	16.12
12.	0.85	6.90	13.78	16.22

The interaction of the protonated form of L-tyrosine could be considered through the following

scheme^a,

It can be shown that

$$k_{obs} \frac{K_a + [H^+]}{[H^+]} = k_1 + \frac{k_2 K_a}{[H^+]} \quad (5)$$

A plot of $k_{obs} \frac{K_a + [H^+]}{[H^+]}$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ was however, found to be non-linear, therefore, the following modified reaction scheme, which gave the best fit with our experimental data was suggested,

where, $K'_1 = k_{21}/k_{32}$. (6)

In this scheme, $\overset{+}{O}NH$ represents the amino acid zwitterion and $\overset{-}{O}N$ represents uninegative ion. In all the species in the scheme, O denotes the carboxylate and N denotes the amino group. The overall rate of the reaction from this reaction scheme is given by equation (7),

$$\text{Rate} = k_{35} [Co \overset{-}{O}N] \quad (7)$$

Rate is also given by equation (8),

$$\text{Rate} = k_{obs} [Co^{II}] [L\text{-Tyrosine}] \quad (8)$$

Since the total concentration of tyrosine is given by equation (8),

$$[L\text{-Tyrosine}] = [\overset{+}{O}NH] + [\overset{-}{O}N] \quad (9)$$

Therefore, equation (8) becomes

$$\text{Rate} = k_{obs} [Co^{II}] \{ [\overset{+}{O}NH] + [\overset{-}{O}N] \} \quad (10)$$

Now, equating equations (7) and (10) and using steady state approximation for $[Co \overset{-}{O}N]$ and $[Co \overset{+}{O}NH]$, the following expression was obtained after rearrangement,

$$k_{obs} \frac{K_1 + [H^+]}{[H^+]} = \frac{(k_{12} + k_{43} K_1 [H^+]^{-1}) k_{35} K'_1}{k_{21} [H^+] + K'_1 (k_{34} + k_{35})} \quad (11)$$

The expected behaviour of the reaction of cobalt(II) and L-tyrosine could be best described by using limiting forms of equation (11).

Using the conditions of low pH, that is $k_{12} \gg k_{43} K_1 [H^+]^{-1}$ and $k_{21} [H^+] \gg K'_1 (k_{34} + k_{35})$, and after taking logarithm on both sides of the equation we get,

$$\log k_{obs} \frac{K_1 + [H^+]}{[H^+]} = \text{pH} + \log \frac{k_{12} k_{35} K'_1}{k_{21} k_{34}} \quad (12)$$

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